

Examining the Role of Pharmacists in Enhancing Medication Reconciliation and Patient Education During Hospital Discharge

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Abstract

Background: Effective medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge are critical for preventing medication errors and improving patient outcomes. Pharmacists play a key role in these processes, but their impact needs further exploration.

Objective: This study examines the role of pharmacists in improving medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge.

Methods: A mixed-methods approach was used. Quantitatively, data were collected from 150 patients to assess medication discrepancies and understanding of discharge instructions before and after pharmacist-led interventions. Qualitatively, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 pharmacists to explore their experiences and perspectives.

Results: Pharmacist-led interventions significantly reduced medication discrepancies from 35 to 12 ($p < 0.01$) and decreased the percentage of patients with discrepancies from 23% to 8% ($p < 0.01$). Patient understanding of discharge instructions improved from 68% to 85% ($p < 0.01$). Qualitative findings revealed that pharmacists effectively addressed challenges such as incomplete medication histories and time constraints, and utilized personalized education to enhance patient understanding.

Conclusion: Pharmacists significantly improve medication reconciliation and patient education during discharge. Their involvement reduces medication discrepancies and enhances patient comprehension of discharge instructions, contributing to better patient outcomes.

Keywords: Medication Reconciliation, Patient Education, Pharmacists, Hospital Discharge, Medication Errors

Introduction

Medication reconciliation and patient education are critical components of the hospital discharge process. Effective medication reconciliation aims to ensure that patients' medication lists are accurate and complete, thereby reducing the risk of medication errors and adverse drug events (ADEs) upon discharge (Ghaibi et al., 2015). Patient education during discharge is equally important as it empowers patients to manage their medications effectively and understand their treatment regimens, contributing to improved adherence and health outcomes (Kripalani et al., 2007).

Despite their importance, medication reconciliation and patient education often face challenges. Studies have shown that discrepancies between hospital and outpatient medication lists are common, with estimates indicating that up to 50% of patients experience medication discrepancies upon discharge (Kwan et al., 2013). Similarly, inadequate patient education has been linked to increased rates of readmissions and medication-related problems (Jack et al., 2009). These challenges underscore the need for effective strategies to improve both processes.

Pharmacists play a pivotal role in addressing these issues. Their expertise in medication management positions them uniquely to contribute to accurate medication reconciliation and comprehensive patient education. Evidence suggests that pharmacist-led medication reconciliation programs can significantly reduce medication errors and improve patient safety (Milfred-LaForest et al., 2013). Additionally, pharmacists'

involvement in patient education has been associated with better understanding of medication regimens and enhanced adherence (Watkins et al., 2012).

This study aims to examine the role of pharmacists in improving medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge. By evaluating pharmacist-led interventions and their impact on these processes, the study seeks to provide insights into how pharmacists can enhance discharge practices and patient outcomes.

Literature Review

Medication Reconciliation: Medication reconciliation is a systematic process designed to ensure that patients' medication lists are accurate and up-to-date across transitions of care, particularly at hospital discharge. The goal is to prevent medication errors, such as omissions, duplications, dosing errors, or drug interactions, which can lead to adverse drug events (ADEs) (Ghaibi et al., 2015). Studies indicate that medication discrepancies are common, with a significant proportion of patients experiencing errors upon discharge (Kwan et al., 2013).

Research has demonstrated that pharmacist-led medication reconciliation programs can effectively reduce these discrepancies. For instance, a study by Milfred-LaForest et al. (2013), found that pharmacist involvement in medication reconciliation significantly decreased medication errors and improved patient safety. Pharmacists' expertise in medication management enables them to identify and resolve discrepancies more effectively than non-pharmacist staff (Kwan et al., 2013).

Patient Education During Discharge: Patient education during hospital discharge is crucial for ensuring that patients understand their treatment regimens and medication instructions. Effective education helps patients manage their medications correctly, adhere to prescribed therapies, and recognize potential side effects or interactions (Kripalani et al., 2007). However, research shows that inadequate discharge education can lead to poor medication adherence and higher rates of hospital readmission (Murray et al., 2007).

Several strategies have been identified to improve patient education during discharge. Structured discharge planning and tailored educational materials have been shown to enhance patients' understanding and adherence to their medication regimens (Kripalani et al., 2007). The involvement of pharmacists in discharge education has been linked to better patient outcomes, including improved medication adherence and reduced readmission rates (Watkins et al., 2012).

Role of Pharmacists in Medication Reconciliation: Pharmacists play a critical role in medication reconciliation due to their extensive knowledge of medications and their potential interactions. Their involvement in the reconciliation process can identify and resolve discrepancies that might otherwise go unnoticed. A study by Kwan et al. (2013) highlighted that pharmacist-led medication reconciliation significantly reduced medication discrepancies and improved patient safety. Pharmacists are adept at conducting thorough medication reviews and communicating with patients and other healthcare providers to ensure continuity of care (Lawrence et al., 2015).

Role of Pharmacists in Patient Education: Pharmacists' involvement in patient education has been shown to improve patient understanding and management of their medications. Research indicates that pharmacist-led education programs can enhance patient knowledge about their medications, leading to better adherence and fewer medication-related problems (Watkins et al., 2012). Pharmacists are skilled at providing clear, concise information and addressing patient questions and concerns, which is essential for effective discharge education (Okumura et al., 2014).

Pharmacists can also contribute to patient education by developing personalized education plans based on individual patient needs and medication regimens. Studies have demonstrated that personalized educational interventions led by pharmacists are more effective than generic discharge instructions in improving patient outcomes and reducing readmission rates (Kripalani et al., 2007).

Summary of Previous Research

Overall, the literature underscores the significant role of pharmacists in enhancing both medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge. Pharmacists' involvement in these processes has been associated with improved medication accuracy, reduced medication errors, and better patient outcomes. However, despite these benefits, challenges remain in integrating pharmacists into discharge processes consistently across healthcare settings (Kwan et al., 2013; Watkins et al., 2012).

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to evaluate the role of pharmacists in improving medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge. The quantitative component assessed the effectiveness of pharmacist-led interventions on medication reconciliation and patient education, while the qualitative component explored pharmacists' perspectives on these interventions.

Setting and Participants: The study was conducted in a tertiary hospital a six-month period. The hospitals were selected based on their diverse patient populations and the presence of established pharmacy services.

Participants

- **Quantitative Component:** A total of 150 patients who were discharged from the hospitals were included in the study. These patients were selected using a convenience sampling method from various medical and surgical wards.
- **Qualitative Component:** Ten pharmacists actively involved in the discharge process were recruited for in-depth interviews. These pharmacists were selected based on their experience and role in medication reconciliation and patient education.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data:

- **Intervention:** Pharmacists implemented a structured medication reconciliation process and provided standardized patient education materials during discharge.
- **Measures:** Data were collected on medication discrepancies, the completeness of medication lists, and patient understanding of discharge instructions. The primary outcome measures included the number of medication discrepancies identified and resolved and patient scores on a discharge education assessment tool, which evaluated their understanding of medication instructions.
- **Procedure:** Medication discrepancies were identified by comparing pre-discharge medication lists with those provided to patients at discharge. Patient understanding was assessed using a validated questionnaire administered within 24 hours of discharge.

Qualitative Data:

- **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the ten participating pharmacists. The interviews explored their experiences with the medication reconciliation process, challenges faced, and perceptions of the effectiveness of patient education interventions.
- **Interview Guide:** The guide included questions on the pharmacists' roles in medication reconciliation, the impact of their interventions, and their views on improving patient education.
- **Procedure:** Interviews were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and insights.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis:

- Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics, medication discrepancies, and patient understanding scores.
- Inferential statistics, including paired t-tests and chi-square tests, were used to evaluate the differences in medication discrepancies and patient understanding before and after the intervention.
- Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Qualitative Analysis:

- Thematic analysis was conducted on the interview transcripts. Initial coding was performed to identify key themes and sub-themes related to the pharmacists' experiences and perceptions.
- Themes were reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represented the data and provided meaningful insights into the role of pharmacists in medication reconciliation and patient education.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the ethics committee. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing patient and pharmacist data, and all recordings and transcripts were securely stored.

Findings

Quantitative Findings

Medication Discrepancies: A total of 150 patients were included in the study. The analysis revealed significant improvements in medication reconciliation following the pharmacist-led intervention.

Measure	Pre-Intervention	Post-Intervention	p-value
Total Medication Discrepancies	35	12	< 0.01
Percentage of Patients with Discrepancies	23%	8%	< 0.01

- **Total Medication Discrepancies:** The number of medication discrepancies identified in patients' discharge medication lists decreased from 35 to 12, representing a significant reduction ($p < 0.01$).
- **Percentage of Patients with Discrepancies:** The proportion of patients with medication discrepancies decreased from 23% to 8% ($p < 0.01$).

Patient Understanding of Discharge Instructions: Patient understanding of discharge instructions was measured using a validated questionnaire. The results showed an improvement in patient knowledge post-intervention.

Measure	Pre-Intervention	Post-Intervention	p-value
Average Score on Discharge Education Assessment	68%	85%	0.01

Average Score on Discharge Education Assessment: Patients' average scores on the discharge education assessment increased from 68% to 85%, indicating a significant improvement in understanding ($p < 0.01$).

Qualitative Findings

Themes and Sub-Themes

Thematic analysis of the semi-structured interviews with ten pharmacists identified several key themes and sub-themes related to their role in medication reconciliation and patient education.

1. Effective Medication Reconciliation

- **Thorough Review Processes:** Pharmacists reported implementing comprehensive medication reviews that identified discrepancies early.
- **Participant A:** "We meticulously compare patients' medication lists from admission to discharge, which helps catch discrepancies before they become issues."
- **Collaborative Communication:** Coordination with other healthcare providers was crucial in resolving discrepancies.
- **Participant B:** "Effective communication with doctors and nurses is essential to ensure that all medication changes are accurately reflected in the discharge plan."

2. Challenges in Medication Reconciliation

- **Incomplete Medication Histories:** Difficulty in obtaining complete medication histories from patients was a common challenge.

- **Participant C:** “Sometimes patients have trouble remembering all their medications, which complicates the reconciliation process.”
- **Time Constraints:** Limited time during discharge planning impacted the thoroughness of medication reconciliation.
- **Participant D:** “We often face time constraints, which can impact how thoroughly we can review medications.”

3. Enhancing Patient Education

- **Personalized Education:** Pharmacists provided tailored educational materials based on individual patient needs.
- **Participant E:** “Personalizing the discharge instructions to each patient's condition and medication helps them understand better.”
- **Improved Communication Techniques:** Use of clear, patient-friendly language and visual aids was effective.
- **Participant F:** “Using visual aids and simple language helps patients grasp their medication regimen more effectively.”

4. Impact of Interventions

- **Increased Patient Satisfaction:** Pharmacists observed higher patient satisfaction with discharge education.
- **Participant G:** “Patients seem more satisfied and less confused about their medications after we implemented the structured education program.”
- **Reduced Readmissions:** There was a noted decrease in hospital readmissions related to medication errors.
- **Participant H:** “We've seen a reduction in readmissions, which we attribute to better medication reconciliation and patient education.”

Discussion

This study highlights the crucial role of pharmacists in improving medication reconciliation and patient education during hospital discharge. The results indicate that pharmacist-led interventions substantially enhance these processes, contributing to better patient outcomes.

Medication Reconciliation: The significant reduction in medication discrepancies, from 35 to 12, and the drop in the percentage of patients with discrepancies from 23% to 8% post-intervention underscore the effectiveness of pharmacist-led medication reconciliation. These results are consistent with previous studies demonstrating that pharmacists' involvement in medication reconciliation reduces medication errors and enhances patient safety (Milfred-LaForest et al., 2013; Kwan et al., 2013). Pharmacists' comprehensive medication reviews and effective communication with other healthcare providers are pivotal in identifying and resolving discrepancies, ensuring accurate medication lists at discharge.

Patient Education: The increase in patient understanding of discharge instructions, with scores improving from 68% to 85%, reflects the positive impact of tailored educational interventions provided by pharmacists. This improvement supports existing literature that highlights the role of pharmacists in enhancing patient education and medication adherence (Watkins et al., 2012; Kripalani et al., 2007). Pharmacists' use of personalized education and clear communication techniques has been shown to improve patient knowledge and reduce the likelihood of medication-related problems and hospital readmissions.

Challenges and Strategies: The qualitative findings reveal several challenges faced by pharmacists, including incomplete medication histories and time constraints. These challenges are consistent with those reported in other studies, which emphasize the need for improved systems and resources to support medication reconciliation (Lawrence et al., 2015). Addressing these challenges requires continued efforts to enhance the integration of pharmacists into the discharge process, ensuring that they have the necessary time and resources to perform thorough medication reviews.

Pharmacists also reported that personalized education and improved communication techniques were effective strategies. These findings align with research suggesting that individualized patient education is more

effective than generic discharge instructions (Okumura et al., 2014). The use of visual aids and patient-friendly language, as reported by participants, contributes to better patient understanding and adherence.

Implications for Practice: The study's findings have several implications for clinical practice. Integrating pharmacists into discharge planning can significantly enhance medication reconciliation and patient education, leading to improved patient outcomes and reduced readmission rates. Hospitals should consider adopting pharmacist-led interventions as a standard practice during discharge processes. Additionally, addressing the identified challenges, such as incomplete medication histories and time constraints, can further enhance the effectiveness of these interventions.

Future Research: Future research should explore the long-term impacts of pharmacist-led interventions on patient outcomes and readmission rates. Larger, multi-center studies could provide further insights into the generalizability of these findings across different settings. Additionally, examining the cost-effectiveness of pharmacist-led interventions could provide valuable information for healthcare administrators and policymakers.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that pharmacist-led medication reconciliation and patient education interventions significantly improve discharge processes. By addressing medication discrepancies and enhancing patient understanding of discharge instructions, pharmacists play a vital role in optimizing patient care and reducing readmission rates. Continued integration of pharmacists into discharge planning and addressing the associated challenges will further enhance the quality of patient care.

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